

Goal	ID	Question	Type	Required? Based on Related Work
Consent	Q1	If you agree to participate in this research, proceed with the survey.		Yes
Demographics	Q2	What is your academic background in software development?		Yes
Demographics	Q3	How many years of professional software development experience do you have?		Yes
Demographics	Q4	What is your gender?		Yes
Demographics	Q5	Which of the following cases is your software development team currently most involved in?		Yes
Demographics	Q6	What programming languages do you work with at the company?		Yes
Demographics	Q7	In the context of your team, is or has a code review been performed?		Yes
Demographics	Q8	Have you used an AI-based programming assistant at your job in the past 12 months?		Yes
RQ1: Reasons to use	Q9	Describe types of situations where you are most successful using AI-based programming assistants in your work.	Open-question	No
RQ1: Reasons to use	Q10	How do you perceive the importance of using AI-based programming assistants in the following situations?	Likert Scale	Yes Liang et al. (2023)
RQ2: Frequency	Q11	Which of the following tools have you worked with in the past 12 months?	Multiple options	Yes
RQ2: Frequency	Q12	How do you estimate how often you use the tools below in a workweek?	Likert Scale	Yes
RQ2: Frequency	Q13	Estimate how often you use AI-based programming assistants (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, etc) in the following situations in a workweek.	Likert Scale	Yes Liang et al. (2023)
RQ3: Challenges	Q14	Describe one or more examples of difficulties or problems you have faced in using AI-based programming assistants in your work.	Open-question	No
RQ3: Challenges	Q15	Considering your experience using AI-based programming assistants, estimate how often you experience the following scenarios per week.	Likert Scale	Yes Liang et al. (2023)
RQ3: Challenges	Q16	Describe one or more examples of strategies you've used to get an AI-based programming assistant to generate the best answers for you.	Open-question	No
RQ4: Reasons not to use	Q17	How much each of the following factors influences your decision not to use AI-based programming assistants (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, etc)?	Likert Scale	Yes Liang et al. (2023)
RQ4: Reasons not to use	Q18	Are there any other important reasons for you not to use an AI-based programming assistant? If yes, please describe these reasons.	Open-question	No
Additional Question	Q19	Considering your current work, estimate how often you use Q&A communities, for instance, Stack Overflow.	Likert Scale	Yes
Additional Question	Q20	How do you see your relationship with Q&A communities, such as Stack Overflow, after the emergence of tools like ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot?	Likert Scale	Yes
Final remarks	Q21	Do you have any other comments about your experience with programming assistants or problems you encountered answering this survey?	Open-question	No
Final remarks	Q22	Can we contact you via email for further questions about our research?	Yes/No	Yes
Final remarks	Q23	If you are available to contribute to our research, please leave your email address:		
Attention Check	-	Please select Strongly Agree to indicate that you are paying attention to this question.		